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RESPONSE OF AS4/PEEK COMPOSITE LATTICE STRUCTURES UNDER THE COMPRESSION AND LOW VELOCITY IMPACT LOADING

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Outline

1. Background
2. Fabrication process
3. Mechanical response
4. Conclusions

1. Background

Fiber Reinforced Composites

—Lightweight and High-Strength Materials

Fig. 1. Dosage of composite material in airliner

Dosage of composite material reached 52%

Fig. 2. A350 XWB

Fig. 3. Tail wing of G650 Aircraft

Fig. 4. Stiffened panel of airliner

Lattice structures

—Lightweight and High-Strength Structures

Fig.5. Comparison of bearing capacity of four sandwich structures (Evans, et al. Prog. Mater. Sci., 2001)

Fig.6. Typical lattice sandwich structures (Wadley, et al. Acta Mater, 2005.)

1. Backgrounds

Previous researches

Metal materials

Thermosetting composites

Metal-Thermosetting hybrid

Fig.7. Traditional lattice structures

Present research work

AS4/PEEK— Advanced thermoplastic composite

AS4/PEEK lattice structure

Novel fabrication process

Mechanical response

2. Fabrication process

Two key issues

- 1) the fabrication of lattice cores;
- 2) the connection of facesheets and cores.

Traditional fabrication technology

Fabrication of lattice cores

Interlocking assembly method

Stamp folding method

Hot pressing method

Facesheet-core connection

Adhesive method

Adhesive

Thermosetting composite / Metal lattice structure

Welding method

Metal lattice structure

Adhesive method

Thermosetting composite lattice structure

2. Fabrication process

AS4/PEEK Material properties :

- 1) repeatable heating forming
- 2) hot melt connection

without additional connecting material (adhesive or solder)

AS4/PEEK lattice structure

Proposed fabrication technology for AS4/PEEK lattice structure

Hot stamping process

Fabrication process of lattice cores

In-situ hot-pressing connection

Facesheet-core connection

3. Mechanical response

Compressive response

Compressive stress-strain curves of AS4/PEEK lattice structures

Compressive failure modes of AS4/PEEK lattice structures

3. Mechanical response

Low-velocity impact response

Impact site

Impact site

Low-velocity impact failure modes of AS4/PEEK lattice structures

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Impact load-time curves of AS4/PEEK lattice structures

4. Conclusions

- A hot stamping process is proposed to fabricate AS4/PEEK lattice cores.
- An *in-situ* hot-pressing connection technology without additional connecting material (adhesive or solder) is proposed to connect facesheets and lattice cores.
- The weak adhesive strength of AS4/PEEK is solved by the in-suit hot-pressing connection technology.
- The failure modes of AS4/PEEK lattice structure were observed under compression loading, including buckling, delamination and fracture of core struts.
- The impact damages of AS4/PEEK lattice structure were observed, which are affected by relative density of core, impact energy and impact position.

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Thank you for your attention

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